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The Final Consumption of Energy in Europe

Between 2000 and 2021 it decreased by 1.23% on average for the countries analyzed

The Eurostat mixes the final consumption of energy. The indicator measures the final use of energy in a country. The consumption of final energy covers only the energy consumed by end users, such as industry, transport, families, services, and agriculture. The final consumption of energy excludes the energy consumption of the energy sector itself and the losses that occur during the transformation and distribution of energy. The indicator is measured in terms of millions of tons of equivalent oil.

Ranking of countries for the value of the consumption of final energy in 2021. Germany is in the first place for the value of the consumption of final energy in 2021 with a value of 209.7 million tons of equivalent oil, followed by France with 143.2, and from Italy with an amount of 113.3 units. In the middle of the standings there are Hungary with an amount of 19.2 units, followed by Portugal with an amount of 15.7, and Greece with an amount of 15.2 units. Estonia closes the ranking with a value of 2.8 units, followed by Cyprus with an amount of 1.7 units and from Malta with 0.6 units.

Ranking of countries by percentage variation of the value of energy consumption between 2000 and 2021. Lithuania is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of the value of energy consumption between 2000 and 2021 with an amount of 50.00% equal to an amount of 1.9 units, followed by Poland with a value of 36.48% equal to an amount of 20.1 units and from Latvia with a value of 24.24% equal to an amount of 0.8 units. In the middle of the standings there are the Czech Republic with an amount of 4.38% equal to an amount of 1.1 units, followed by Slovakia with an amount of 3.64% equal to an amount of 0.4 units, and Slovenia with an amount of 2.17% equal to an amount of 0.1 units. The classrooms close the ranking with an amount of -10.5% equal to an amount of -5.5 units, followed by Portugal with a value of -12.78% equal to an amount of -2.3 units and by the Greece with a value of -19.15% equal to an amount of -3.6 units. In summary, the value of the percentage variation of the value of energy consumption between 2000 and 2021 has decreased by a value equal to -1.23%.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Specifically, three Clusters are identified or:

- Cluster 1: Slovakia, Bulgaria, Ireland, Croatia, Denmark, Slovenia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Estonia, Portugal, Hungary, Cyprus, Greece, Malta, Romania, Czech Republic, Finland, Austria, Sweden, Belgium;
- Cluster 2: Germany, France;
- Cluster 3: Spain, Poland, Italy, the Netherlands.

From the point of view of the value of the median of the cluster, the following order is: C2 = 176.45 > C3 = 77.75 > C1 = 11.4.

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Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is presented below with Euclidean distance. Specifically, three different network structures are identified, one of which are a complex and two simplified.

There is a network structure with the structure indicated below:

- Latvia has a connection with Lithuania for a value of 0.061 units, with Luxembourg for a value of 0.015 units with Slovenia for an amount of 0.063 units;
- Luxembourg has a connection with Slovenia for an amount of 0.015 units, with Lithuania for an amount of 0.051 units and with Slovenia for an amount of 0.051 units;
- Slovenia has a concession with Luxemburg for an AM, mounting 0.051 units, with Latvia for an amount of 0.063 units and with Lithuania for an amount of 0.032 units;
- Lithuania has a connection with Latvia for an amount of 0.061 units, with Luxembourg for an amount of 0.051 units and with Slovenia for an amount of 0.032 units.

There are also two following structures with simplified networks or:

- Slovakia and Ireland have a connection equal to a value of 0.066 units;
- The Czech Republic and Ireland have a connection for a value of 0.041 units.

Conclusion. The final consumption of energy has decreased between 2000 and 2021 on average for the European countries considered. The reduction of the final consumption of energy was particularly relevant in the period between 2019 and 2020 or during the pandemic period due to the closure of many companies and the breakdown of international supply chains. There are some countries that have increased the final consumption of energy such as in the case of Eastern countries. The increase in the final consumption of energy also indicates a propensity for the growth of the gross domestic product. However, the development of new technologies can allow economic systems to grow in productivity also by reducing the value of the final consumption of energy.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Rank	Country	2021	Rank	Country	2021
1	<i>Germany</i>	209,7	15	<i>Greece</i>	15,2
2	<i>France</i>	143,2	16	<i>Denmark</i>	13,8
3	<i>Italy</i>	113,3	17	<i>Ireland</i>	11,4
4	<i>Spain</i>	80,3	18	<i>Slovakia</i>	11,4
5	<i>Poland</i>	75,2	19	<i>Bulgaria</i>	10,3
6	<i>Netherlands</i>	46,9	20	<i>Croatia</i>	7
7	<i>Belgium</i>	35,9	21	<i>Lithuania</i>	5,7
8	<i>Sweden</i>	31,7	22	<i>Slovenia</i>	4,7
9	<i>Austria</i>	27,8	23	<i>Latvia</i>	4,1
10	<i>Czechia</i>	26,2	24	<i>Luxembourg</i>	4,1
11	<i>Romania</i>	25,4	25	<i>Estonia</i>	2,8
12	<i>Finland</i>	24,9	26	<i>Cyprus</i>	1,7
13	<i>Hungary</i>	19,2	27	<i>Malta</i>	0,6
14	<i>Portugal</i>	15,7			

Country	2000	2021	Var Ass	Var Per
Belgium	37,7	35,9	-1,80	-4,77
Bulgaria	9,1	10,3	1,20	13,19
Czechia	25,1	26,2	1,10	4,38
Denmark	14,7	13,8	-0,90	-6,12
Germany	220,2	209,7	-10,50	-4,77
Estonia	2,4	2,8	0,40	16,67
Ireland	10,8	11,4	0,60	5,56
Greece	18,8	15,2	-3,60	-19,15
Spain	80	80,3	0,30	0,37
France	154,8	143,2	-11,60	-7,49
Croatia	6	7	1,00	16,67
Italy	124,8	113,3	-11,50	-9,21
Cyprus	1,7	1,7	0,00	0,00
Latvia	3,3	4,1	0,80	24,24
Lithuania	3,8	5,7	1,90	50,00
Luxembourg	3,5	4,1	0,60	17,14
Hungary	16,2	19,2	3,00	18,52
Malta	0,5	0,6	0,10	20,00
Netherlands	52,4	46,9	-5,50	-10,50
Austria	23,7	27,8	4,10	17,30
Poland	55,1	75,2	20,10	36,48
Portugal	18	15,7	-2,30	-12,78
Romania	22,7	25,4	2,70	11,89
Slovenia	4,6	4,7	0,10	2,17
Slovakia	11	11,4	0,40	3,64
Finland	24,4	24,9	0,50	2,05
Sweden	35	31,7	-3,30	-9,43